

**CARE FOR OUR COMMON HOME:
A HOPEFUL ENCOUNTER OF BEAUTY
AND JOY TOWARDS STEWARDSHIP**

ABSTRACT

In today's world, there is urgency in relation to the call for ecological conversion—a call that concerns present and future generations. Considering such a need, this project aims to strengthen the teaching of stewardship to Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig. In this way, students are invited to recognize stewardship as a moral imperative—an opportunity for a hopeful encounter of finding beauty and joy in creation that reinforces an awareness of the interconnectedness of all creatures of God. Consequently, it also aims to enjoin them to take part in positive action to bring about change concerning the environment. This paper presents three ground plans—one for Doctrine, Morals and Worship—each following the National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines' methodological principles of integration, inculturation and community-forming. Drawing wisdom from *Laudato Si*, this paper hopes to provide students with a better understanding of creation that echoes the expressed commitment of a Church journeying toward ecological conversion.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

*The earth mourns and fades,
the world languishes and fade....*

–Isaiah 24:4

Using the prophecy of Isaiah, God’s creation today is lamenting as never before. The environment is in crisis and action is needed urgently by everyone. People and nations need an ecological conversion and we need to be good stewards of this amazing earth, we call our home. Despite all these issues, we can still change the course of history, because our faith is one that wants creation to be cherished and renewed.

A beautiful world which is our “common home is like a sister with whom we share our life and beautiful mother who opens her arms to embrace us.”¹ This common home is provided to us by God who creates us with love. With this love springs the abundance of other creations such as food, water, lands in which we can work, grow, rest, and recreate to enjoy our lives. For us to be able to create a more personal relationship with Jesus as part of God’s creation, we need to connect to our roots. We need to “get new strength to care for others and for creation.”²

This project aims to intensify the teaching of stewardship to Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig. In this way, the students will find essence in the reality that stewardship is a moral responsibility. Consequently, it aims to enjoin them to take part in positive action to bring about change. Using a part of the *Laudato Si* will give my

¹ Pope Francis, *Laudato Si* (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2015), para.1

² Ibid., para. 217.

students a better understanding of our connectedness with the rest of the creation and the expressed commitment of the Church to a journey to ecological conversion. In addition, this project will reinforce awareness of our interconnection with other creations that all have the part to take care of our Common Home.

There is urgency with the call for ecological conversion as it concerns everyone and the future generations. That is why I dedicate this capstone project so my son and the future generation will be able to enjoy our Common Home where they can be able to fulfill their mission as a human being created in God's image and likeness. They will also take the same unifying actions in taking steps in caring for our Common Home.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The project, specifically seeks to answer the question: "How do we teach Grade 7 students of CLVE subject that stewardship is part of their moral responsibility?" The problem lies with the misconception of the student's notion on the phrase "crown of God's creation" of not having the inclination to care for the common home because of how they see themselves as not directly part of the community of creation. They do not fully see themselves as beautiful, true and good. With this, there is a need to intensify teaching the Grade 7 students their own, natural, God-given identity as "image and likeness" (Genesis 1:26) of God so that caring for the Common Home becomes natural in them. All life on earth is God's creation and we are called to take good care of creation as Genesis 1:2, "till it and keep it."

Human beings are entrusted by God to take care of the world we live in. We are empowered to take possession but at the same time, it comes with great responsibility and accountability. "The destruction of the human environment is extremely serious, not only because God entrusted the world to us men and women, but because human

life is itself a gift which must be defended from various ways of debasement.”³ This means that we need to acknowledge our responsibility as the crown of God’s creation to seek oneness and solidarity for a hopeful encounter of beauty and joy towards stewardship. “A loving awareness that we are not disconnected from the rest of creatures, but joined in a splendid universal communion.”⁴

Having been created by God in His image and likeness, we need to embrace the beautiful truth that it is innate in each one of us to partake in caring for the Common Home. Students started to take responsibilities in their daily and simple choices such as buying products that are long lasting, engaging in the markets, practicing reuse, reduce, recycle at home. School reinforces the good practices of the students from their respective homes, and they can help others understand the importance and value of our common home. The community will support linkages and get involved in the protection of the common home. Conscience “is gradually shaped through all the many and complex factors”⁵ in which students witness and get involved in their countless encounters with other people from home, school and community. Thus, formation of one’s conscience towards Caring for the Common Home -the Earth takes a great part in the fulfillment of stewardship. Unifying efforts of school, home and community will help form the conscience of students which leads to glorifying the Creator.

³ Ibid., para. 5.

⁴ Ibid., para. 220.

⁵ Catholic Bishops’ Conference of the Philippines, *Catechism for Filipino Catholics* (Manila: ECCCE/ Word and Life, 2012), para. 704.

SCOPE AND LIMITATION

This project focuses on the importance of the students' understanding of their identity as "image and likeness" of God and their role as stewards in caring for the Common Home of the Grade 7 students in St. Paul College Pasig.

The audience is limited to Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig in the subject Christian Living and Values Education (CLVE). There are three Ground Plans created, one in each Dimension- for Doctrine entitled "God Creates and Sustains Everything that Exists," for Morals entitled "Formation of Christian Conscience" and for Worship entitled "Caring for God's Creation."

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This project will be helpful for the following:

Catholic Faith. This will help intensify the teaching that human beings are part of creation and since we are created good by God it is innate to care for the Common Home. This also means that we need to see our relationship with ourselves and others, especially the poor who are greatly affected by the ecological crisis such as urban poor people who are affected when there is flood due to typhoon, as well as farmers. Thus, the faithful will advocate environmental stewardship as a connection in glorifying God. The flourishing of creation is part of the whole economy of salvation; respect and deeper connection with creation lead us to greater communion with God.

Church. This project will help in their pursuit of the advocacy on environmental stewardship geared towards sustainability. As Pope Francis urgently appealed in his encyclical on *Laudato Si* to involve everyone in a new dialogue that involves everyone

as he states, “all of us can cooperate as instruments of God for the care of creation, each according to his or her own culture, experience, involvements and talents.”⁶

Religious Education. This project will validate their teaching to a more solid and intense integration of caring for the Common Home. It will be a topic discussed in each level from Grade 7 to Grade 12 CLVE subjects. This will also help raise awareness of the effects of the ecological crisis which demands a concrete plan of action to be materialized.

Students. This will encourage them to continue to participate in the universal advocacy of caring for our common home. Their good practices at home will be intensified in school and will bring them to initiate projects and advocacies that protect, care and preserve our Common Home. This will also urge them to use their God-given talents, skills, and interests to respond to God’s call in taking care of His creation and invite others to do the same.

Teachers. This will encourage them to adopt or design lessons pattern from the Ground Plans mentioned in Chapter 3 of this project. They as part of God’s creation will intensify their stewardship so they will serve as role models to their students such as turning off lights when not in used, using aircon in a limited hour and maximum of 25 degree Celsius temperature, practicing reuse, reduce, recycle, continuous use of ecobags, etc.

School. This will encourage them to intensify or reevaluate the existing program of the school on environmental stewardship. This means they will continue to initiate conservation efforts and sustainable projects to provide platforms for the members of the community to participate and contribute their resources.

⁶ Pope Francis, *Laudato Si*, para. 14.

Nation. This will encourage everyone to be accountable in their action and to acknowledge that anything we do to—preserve, sustain, or destroy our Common Home will directly affect our lives most extensively experienced by the poor.

METHODOLOGY

This project started on the first summer, taking the course ReEd 215 online class: *Readings in Doctrine*, under the supervision of Dr. Patricia P. Lambino. It started with the composition of the Teaching Statement answering the question: “What I do to Educate People Toward Maturity in Faith?”. The book of Thomas H. Groome entitled “Will there be Faith?” was the basis in the composition of the Teaching Statement. The teaching statement serve as the driving force in the creation of the Ground Plans. The first Ground Plan is on DOCTRINE for Grade 7 entitled “God Creates and Sustains Everything that Exists” is a class encounter for 1 session that runs for 50 minutes.

On the second summer, taking the course ReEd 297.3 online class: *Readings in Moral Theology* under the supervision of Dr. Rachel Joyce Marie Sanchez. The Teaching Statement was critiqued, evaluated, and revised. Part of the process was to determine the alignment and misalignment of the teaching statements to the Ground Plans developed in the course. In the third part of my teaching philosophy, I stated “FIRE EXCELLENCE” which I got from our school’s vision statement. I thought of re-direction or putting a new meaning of excellence and omitting the word “fire” and change it to “aspire”. “Fire” is a strong word that demands urgency of direction while “aspire” according to Merriam Webster “is to seek to attain or accomplish a particular goal.” “*Fire excellence in all areas of life*” is exhausting all means and ways to give and provide excellence while neglecting human frailty. This pandemic opened our eyes to the reality that in our frailty we still find God journeying with God. It needs humility

to accept to let go and let God in control. There is excellence in humbling that human interests are limited when God decides. I think the long-debated vision statement of our school must embrace its weakness that it cannot accompany all stakeholders in all seasons of life. The MORALS Ground Plan for Grade 7 entitled “Formation of Christian Conscience” was created to also highlight that as a teacher I can be with my students as they continually form, shape, and educate their conscience.

On the third summer, taking the course ReEd 297.4 online class: *Readings in Worship and Spirituality* under the supervision of Dr. Justin Joseph Badion. The teaching statement was re-evaluated and revised to connect its relevance in the WORSHIP Ground Plan for Grade 7 entitled entitled “Care for the Common Home” is a paraliturgy for 50 minutes. There were added parts such as “Religious Education as my mother” to highlight the importance of my personal experiences that led me to love my vocation as a teacher. I also added the last part “Note of Hope” to acknowledge that there are elements in our vocation that we need to “let go and let God” do God’s will.

Looking at the whole perspective with the help of the Teaching Statements and Ground Plans, the title was made “Care for Common Home: Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig will embrace their Role as Crown of God's Creation in the form of Stewardship working for Common Home” and the problem was stated “How do we teach Grade 7 students of Christian Living and Values Education subject that stewardship is part of their moral responsibility?” It then trimmed to one audience who are the Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig.

ORGANIZATION

This capstone project contains several chapters. “Chapter 1: Introduction” stating the problem and the background as why there is need to intensify teaching

stewardship to Grade 7 students. To highlight that God loves us so much and all God's creation is good and has a purpose. God wants us to relate with one another, value our interconnection with other created things and do our responsibility to take care our Common Home.

“Chapter 2: What I Do When I Educate People Toward Maturity In Faith” is the teaching statement elaborating my journey until Religious Education was introduced to me. This includes the emphasis of the impact of Religious Education in my personal life, the demands and relevance of the vocation in the holistic transformation of the students. This chapter will navigate my continuous journey as a Religious Educator.

“Chapter 3: The Ground Plans” presents the greater elaboration of the Religious Educator featuring the discussion on Creation, Formation of Conscience and Paraliturgy. This chapter begins with the context of the target audience.

“Chapter 4: Methodology” presents the methodological principles in the NCDP in creating Ground Plans for Grade 7 students. Methods based on the “Good News”—“based from the law of three fidelities as outlined by the NCDP- fidelity to God, fidelity to man, and the fidelity to the Church, the Pedagogy of Faith for Filipinos Today follows three basic catechetical principles: integration, inculturation, and community forming.”⁷

The dialogue partner of the NCDP methodological principles is the teaching statement in Chapter 2. This elaborates how Integration in its forms and applications (Life Dimension, Structural Integration, Dimension Integration, Source Integration,

⁷ Catholic Bishops' Conference of the Philippines, *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines* (Manila: ECCCE, 2007), para. 355.

Subject Integration, and Environmental Integration), Inculturation and Community-Forming Features.

“Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations” gives the summary of the project and the writers recommendation for further works on the topic.

CHAPTER II

TEACHING STATEMENT

WHAT I DO WHEN I EDUCATE PEOPLE TOWARD MATURITY IN FAITH

RELIGIOUS EDUCATION AS MY MOTHER

I am the eldest of 6 siblings and I was 14 years old when my parents got separated. We were raised by my grandmother and grew up without a mother by our side. The hardships of life opened opportunities for me to continue my studies through a scholarship program for a Religious Education course. The journey wasn't easy, especially that at first, I enrolled in the course because it was the only one offered. The world of Religious Education is very difficult and if given other options, I will not choose it. It is in this sense that I am reminded of this verse from Matthew 22:14 which states: "Many are invited, but few are chosen."

I feel like choosing Religious Education was my destiny. It was as if I was drawn to it. Little by little, I found myself learning and being nurtured by the course I chose to take. Religious Education became like a mother to me. It taught me lessons on how to live my life. "Religious Education, in particular, should enable people to reflect critically on their own lives in the world, lend ready and well-informed access to the faith and then to make judgements and decisions about its truths and spiritual wisdom for their lives."⁸ Religious Education took the place of my absent parents. It provided

⁸ Groome, Thomas, *Will There Be Faith? A New Vision for Educating and Growing Disciples* (New York, NY: Harper One, 2011), 97-98.

an avenue to look at things from a positive perspective. I did not just learn about life, but it gives me life.⁹

Using the imagery of a mother, this is relatable in how Pope Francis describes common home as “beautiful mother who opens her arms to embrace us”¹⁰ Growing up in the Northern part of Cebu, we are surrounded by beautiful nature such as sugar cane, trees, bamboo, coconuts, cornfields, and beaches. I am always awed by God’s creation and I always feel calm, connected, and at peace when I am immersed in nature—a true encounter of beauty and joy. In fact, most of my memorable experiences in life are one with nature. In my elementary years, my father was always out for racket since he does not have a permanent job when I miss him I stared at the sugar cane field that are so green that brings hope in my heart that soon my father will go home. When I am tired in school, I always climbed our santol or cotton fruit tree and ponder as I stare from afar at the green scenery and I would feel one with nature. When I was 9 years old, I remembered my aunt came to bring the sad news that my Lolo passed away, I was on top of the star fruit tree as I processed my feelings. Every summer, I would join my brothers in playing kites in the newly harvested field of sugarcane. Group projects in TLE where we need to plant seedlings and make them grow until it bears fruit, so while we collaborate to take good care of them, we fertilize them using the cow’s manure as organic fertilizer. Every birthday we would go to the beach and swim even on Easter Sunday. We bring food and make grilled pork on the seashore, and we clean as we go. Even when there are typhoons, classes are suspended so we are all gathered as a family eager to listen to our Lola’s stories back in World War II. Our Common Home is our

⁹ See *Ibid.*, 94.

¹⁰ Pope Francis, *Laudato Si* (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2015), para.1

mother who witnesses all my ups and downs and respects me by allowing me to be immersed in them, to be one with them—a true encounter of peace and joy.

EMBRACE THE VOCATION

In conversations of adults, one topic that normally pops out is about one's profession. When I get the chance to be in one, I proudly say that I am a teacher. People who are from different professions are usually awed and would ask my major or which field of specialization, and my answer would be "Christian Living." Most often than not, I can sense the short pause because they are trying to figure out what it is, and so I aptly add: "It's like Values Education." That's the time they get to understand it and exclaim with a resounding "*aha*" followed with the additional statement: "*this means you are a good person or a holy person.*"

Teaching is the noblest profession. Every teacher is obliged to know the multifaceted situations, races, cultures, and family backgrounds of the students. The teacher interacts and designs lessons that they think are suited to all, whether they have 5 or 55 students. "The Church sends catechists, teachers of the faith, to faithfully echo the mystery of divine love in each age and to every generation. Their ministry comes from the mission of Jesus as sent by the Father."¹¹ I believe I cannot give what I do not have. So, as part of my mission, I live by the principle that teachers are lifelong learners. I exhaust all means to help my students because this is not just a profession but a vocation to form them into good Christians who live out the values of Jesus. Being both a teacher and a student at the same time, I am at the same pace with my students. I can

¹¹ Natividad, Maria Lucia C., *Teaching the Faith: Renewal in Religious Education in the Philippines* (Quezon City: Claretian Communications Foundation, Inc., 2018), 25.

relate to them as I feel what they feel, being eager to learn things that would satisfy curiosity, and to unveil messages of God from my experiences to draw out wisdom.

The “*aha*” and the additional statement “*this means you are a good person or a holy person*” remind me that in proclaiming Jesus to others, I am at the forefront and I serve as an instrument to make Jesus alive in all my encounters with my students. I remember a session in a retreat I attended with Father Jason Laguerta when he compared us (teachers) to the flying trapeze where there is a flyer and a catcher. The flyer entertains people and is applauded because of the best skills he/she shows, while the catcher ensures the safety of the flyer and is often left unnoticed. We, educators are like the flyer: we teach about Jesus by exhausting all our means, showing our talents and skills that would make people drawn towards Jesus. We mesmerize them with the grace God has given us through the lessons we teach them. On the other hand, he likened the catcher to God because it is Him who makes sure that we are safe. He always supports, helps, loves, and accepts us. “Therefore, catechesis is not about the catechist’s personal opinion and attitudes, but of Jesus’s revelation, and is not directed toward one’s person but to Jesus.”¹²

Despite the efforts of religious educators like me, the moral issues our country is facing at present challenge me as a teacher. To address these concerns, I engage myself in dialogue, “Before all else, dialogue is a manner of acting, an attitude and a spirit which guides one’s conduct. It implies concern, respect, and hospitality towards the other. It leaves room for the other person’s identity, his modes of expression, and his values. Dialogue is thus the norm and necessary manner of every form of Christian mission, as well as of every aspect of it, whether one speaks of simple presence and

¹² Ibid.

witness, service, or direct proclamation”¹³. In this manner, total respect and a listening heart are the things that I gave to my students who may have doubts about the faith and are likely to question some of the Church teachings.

Furthermore, I observe that my students are growing in a world full of uncertainties and depravity. They are facing a critical era where inner identity or beauty is difficult to reach. They tend to find happiness from the outside because they fail to be in touch with their core and recognize their purpose. A lot of our students have unsuccessfully attained “wisdom process—“thinking for themselves” they don't want to be in silence. One reason perhaps is their fear that even when they keep still, they will still be confronted with all realities of their lives, ending up not knowing how to process things on their own. Many have chosen to “not trying to know” because they are not equipped on how to unveil God’s message in their lives. That is why others would resort to self-harm, anxiety, depression, and worst of all, taking their own lives. With all these said, I am even more challenged and very much eager to help my students grow into better individuals by guiding them and explaining to them the many questions they have in mind. In situations like these, they need “mothering” to feel support, validation, and guide to reach a certain maturity in dealing with crucial phases in life, if their parents or mothers cannot provide this to them. This entails the call for Synodality “that it indicates the path along which the People of God walk together.”¹⁴

Witnessing my students thrive in their multifaceted aspects of life, I believe that they need to have a place, a Common Home to continue their quest for meaning and

¹³ Federation of Asian Bishops’ Conference, *Dialogue and Mission*, 29

¹⁴ “Synodality in the Life and Mission of the Church (International Theological Commission),” 2018, para. 3, accessed August 10, 2022, <http://secretariat.synod.va/content/synod/en/news/synodality-in-the-life-and-mission-of-the-church--by-the-interna.html>.

purpose. Putting in mind the explanation of Pope Francis in *Laudato Si* seeing environment as a “relationship between nature and the society which lives in it. Nature cannot be regarded as something separate from ourselves or as a mere setting in which we live. We are part of nature, included in it and this in constant interaction in it.”¹⁵ With the actual situation of our Common Home, like with a simple rain which leads to the suspension of classes due to flood because of the clogged drainage, soil erosion due to deforestation, air pollution triggering sensitive students who have asthma and lung sickness, and the likes, we need to face and act upon these and indeed, this is an added task. “We have come to see ourselves as her lords and masters, entitled to plunder her at will. The violence present in our hearts, wounded by sin, is also reflected in the symptoms of sickness evident in the soil, in the water, in the air and in all forms of life.”¹⁶ The world and everything in it show the overflowing love of God for all His creation. This love of God comes with trust in human beings to take care of His creation- the call for stewardship to come together for sustainable goals and preservation efforts. I acknowledge my moral responsibility as a steward and as an educator, I need to take care of our Common Home for my students’ well-being.

With all these said, teaching is truly a tough vocation. Still, I believe God is with me in this journey and I am commissioned by Jesus just as how He commissioned His apostles in Matthew 28:19-20 when He said: “Go therefore, and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all that I have commanded you. And behold, I am with you always, until the end of the very age.” In the end, what matters are the hearts that

¹⁵ Pope Francis, *Laudato Si*, para. 139.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, para. 2.

sees God who faithfully journeys with His people. And as much as He loves His children, I am sure that He is constantly with me in my vocation and in my quest to protect our Common Home not just for my students at present, as well as for the future generation that will lead them to encounter true beauty and joy with God's creation.

GO WITH THE SEASONS OF LIFE

There are highs and lows in life that make us stop, look around and reflect. Often, we hear others say that things will happen in God's perfect time. As Ecclesiastes 3:1 goes: "There is time for everything." Time requires process and Groome mentioned that education can be in the three levels of process: learn about it, learn from it and becoming.

Learn about it—I am eternally grateful for the opportunity that has blessed me for the past 9 years in my vocation as a Paulinian lay collaborator. Because of St. Paul College, Pasig, I have developed professionally with the experiences I have gained and the people I have encountered. I was equipped with skills and I continue to learn more things that I would need in dealing with the students, parents, colleagues, and other people in the institution. Attending seminars and workshops for the new curriculum offered in school, taking an administrative role for the first time this year, being a new mother and a wife to my small family, and not to forget my responsibilities as a Religious Educator: all these I get to juggle at the same time and yet find balance and calmness in this game called life, with the grace of God.

Learn from it—I have given my utmost effort in promoting our school's thrusts and in leading the students towards holistic development by designing lessons that will focus on the outcome, the "being" or "becoming" of the learners, and not just with their outputs. I was able to share my giftedness as a person and inspire others to live as true

Paulinians. I proved myself in pursuing this dream of mine to become a good teacher who will teach not just academics but also notable virtues to the students throughout this journey. I always attribute it to my Paulinian education which honed me to be the best Religious educator for my students, at all times.

Becoming—I serve as a role model to others whenever I show mindfulness during the praying of the rosary in school, or when I encourage others to pause and pray the Angelus at noon time. I make sure that I follow the rules and regulations of the school and support the school all the way. I maintain my professionalism in all my dealings with the stakeholders of the school. I nourish the passion within me by being innovative and creative as I improve my teaching strategies. I continue to share my time and value as well the time of my students who have problems in life by listening and giving pieces of advice. Indeed, there is time for everything as long as we embrace the processes and seasons of life.

I saw the importance of my journey as a teacher because it also challenges my principles and help me assess my unique personal qualities, thinking processes, talents, and skills, teaching me how strengthening them can open doors to continued learning and personal fulfillment.

ASPIRE EXCELLENCE

I aspire for excellence by affirmatively doing my work with my utmost effort, love and quality guided by the school's vision: *"St. Paul College Pasig is an internationally recognized Catholic school for girls that shapes character, nurtures*

God-given talents and fires excellence in all areas of life.”¹⁷ I go beyond “fire excellence.” I ASPIRE EXCELLENCE, as I realized that aspiring is seeking ways to attain excellence with the available resources, respecting the capabilities of the person in a specific situation that s/he is facing. The word “fire” implies strong energy or competition which is applicable in corporate areas, but not in a Catholic setting. Not that I am saying that we must not teach students to compete, but for me, we need to teach students that we embrace process to achieve holistic formation. The process may be favorable or unfavorable for us but we need to accept it, just like what we are facing this pandemic. We cannot afford to just focus on “fire excellence” because of the so many limitations that hinder us to see what is beyond the respective houses of our students. To aspire excellence is more inclusive as it considers all types of learners.

As an educator, I can aspire excellence by the enhancement of classroom instruction through the following measures: engaging learning activities that will elicit optimum student participation and interaction and sustain the students’ enthusiasm by interactive activities, collaborative learning groups, reflection writing, and sharing human experiences. Short clip videos, music videos, and picture analysis may be used as varied motivational activities. Substantial deepening of subject matter coverage by relating bible stories to daily life experiences or applying life to faith is also important. Greater use of the discovery and experimental approach to enhance the critical thinking and creative thinking skills of the students by open-ended questions or using generative themes and situational analysis is a strategy that I also practice. Integration of current and relevant issues in the lessons to intensify the social consciousness of students using

¹⁷ St. Paul College Pasig, “Home”. St. Paul College Pasig. Accessed September 16, 2019. <https://www.spcpasig.edu.ph/>.

magazines like FISH, Kerygma, Family Matters, and using interactive strategies for the topics using online apps are very useful for my student who use Multiple Intelligences in sharing meaningful synthesis of the lessons.

To address this, I applied Kainonia: Strategy 1-Getting people involved in the life and ministries of the parish.¹⁸ “Getting people, including children and youth, actively involved in serving their faith community will nurture their own faith as well.” For the students to be holistically formed not just for academics and extra-curricular activities, we also entrust them to the people in the parish, so that they can engage themselves in the formation of their faith. During the pre-pandemic years, all our high school students experience the parish involvement. They serve as greeters, lectors and commentators, choir members, collectors, and others. In school, we have liturgical ministries to revive and synergize our students to serve and to share their skills. It is a platform that provides ways to evangelize the faithful virtually or physically.

“Religious Education has to be systematic. It means, first of all, teaching that is programmed for a definite goal—not merely arranged in a haphazard or improvised manner. Such programming refers not only to the subject matter—the truths of faith—but also to age, background, and capacities of students.”¹⁹ This is to note that excellence must target the holistic being of the students which corresponds to the 3 Dimensions of Faith—Doctrine, Morals and Worship.

¹⁸ Thomas Groome, *Will there Be Faith: A New Vision for Educating and Growing Disciples* (New York: Harper One 2011), 169

¹⁹ Natividad, Maria Lucia C., *Teaching the Faith: Renewal in Religious Education in the Philippines*, 43.

NOTE OF HOPE

Despite the adversities, difficulties, challenges, and uncontrolled fluctuation of life's flow of a teacher it is best to always be reminded of the purpose of Religious Education- the heart of our mission is Jesus Christ, who sees us, loves us, and holds us closely and dearly to Him helping us to achieve the mission. May the school motto of St. Paul College Pasig—*Caritas Christi Urget Nos* (the charity of Christ impels us) serve as the guiding force in the attainment of the “aha” moments of my students in their true encounter with Jesus, through their formal and informal encounters with me as their teacher. Consequently, may they find beauty and joy as they exercise stewardship for our Common Home.

CHAPTER III

THE GROUND PLANS

The Ground Plans presented are intended for the Grade 7 Junior High School students at St. Paul College Pasig. I selected this level since it is their first entry into High School life bringing with them different knowledge of the Catholic Faith. The Ground Plans made are two teaching materials for Doctrine Dimension and Morals Dimension while for Worship Dimension it is in a form of paraliturgy.

CONTEXT OF THE GRADE 7 STUDENTS OF ST. PAUL COLLEGE PASIG

The Grade 7 all-girls students with the age range from 11-13 years old. Most of them come from a well-off families whose parents owned businesses, OFW (Overseas Filipino Workers) or professionals. Most of the family consists of both parents, some have distant parents due to work abroad and some come from a broken family in which a single mother or father or a grandparent is only present.

For Religion Affiliation, most are Catholics- born, raised, and practicing while few are non-practicing Catholics. There are students who belong to other religions such as Born Again, Methodist, Protestants, Iglesia ni Cristo, Kingdom Citizen, and a few who would claim Atheists. Around 97% of the population came from the Grade School Department of St. Paul College Pasig while 3% comes from a neighboring school that opted for a big community for learning, a change of residency, and some were recruited by some teachers or parents. The Grade 7 sections are composed of a range from 6-9 sections. These students love the integrated curriculum of the school especially G.I.F.T.

(Giftedness Instruction for Talent) Program which gives them an avenue to showcase their God-given talents, skills, and interests.

On the other hand, Grade 7 who are in the early adolescence stage, face a lot of changes already such as fitting in, stereotyping, and status quo which sometimes made them feel weary. They need to feel that they are seen, heard and loved. The criterion on discernment applies to these students who face these complex modern conditions, with new sensitivities (e.g., solidarity, social justice, peace), new demands and hopes (equal rights, liberation movements, feminism), moral judgments are more difficult and less certain however, they must be hopeful that life is a learning process.²⁰

With the pandemic, education change its course. What was impossible before is made possible and education becomes accessible to all students and distance is not a problem. In these changing normals, the school embraces the new learning modalities where some students are onsite while others are purely online, especially those who live outside Metro Manila. This kind of set-up which we call a *hyflex* class continues to nourish their faith through activities such as Class Mass, Retreats, Recollections, and Outreaches. In the pre-pandemic classroom set-up, I would see some students who were sleepy and uninterested in my lesson. I saw the difference now; I saw the thirst for hearing God's message in relation to their experiences during the pandemic. Their realizations became deep and the different image of God in their varied journey is also growing and changing.

In pre-pandemic, there are good programs advocating protection and preservation of environment. These programs are supported by unifying efforts from

²⁰ "Pontifical Biblical Commission The Bible and Morality: Biblical Roots of Christian Conduct," 2008, para. 154, accessed January 17, 2023, https://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/congregations/cfaith/pcb_documents/rc_con_cfaith_doc_20080511_bibbia-e-morale_en.html.

students, teachers, parents and barangays. One of the programs is called Reviving State of Water in Rivers, Creeks, and Drainage through “Bokashi Balls” or mabuhay balls. “A bokashi ball, also known as ‘mabuhay ball,’ is a Japanese rehabilitation technology made up of all-organic materials, such as garden soil, molasses, and rice hull. It has an effective microorganism solution that breaks down toxins and consumes bad bacteria in the water.”²¹ Students and teachers did all the process in school while parents needed to make seven “bokashi balls” at home. Some of the teachers will determine which barangay needs support in reviving their state of water. Then, students, teachers and parents will conduct a seminar to the people in the barangay on how to make the “bokashi balls” in which they successfully did. Lastly, the “bokashi balls” from the SPCP and from the barangays were scheduled to be thrown to the water. It was monitored by the Community Extension Services for the monitoring of the progress and its effectivity of it. During the pandemic up to now, these projects were made by Grade 12 students and only mentioned as part of the discussion in the Grade 7 students in their Christian Living Education subject.

DESIGNING THE GROUND PLANS

The DOCTRINE Ground Plan for Grade 7 entitled “God Creates and Sustains Everything that Exists” is a class encounter for 1 session that runs for 50 minutes. This Ground Plan was created in the RelEd 215 online class: *Readings in Doctrine*, under the supervision of Dr. Patricia P. Lambino. This aim to address the problem of Grade 7 “students do not believe that they are innately good in result they do not see their

²¹ “Dnr Uses ‘Bokashi Balls’ To Improve Boracay Wetland’s Water Quality” (May 7, 2022), accessed February 14, 2023, <https://www.dnr.gov.ph/index.php/news-events/press-releases/3923-dnr-uses-bokashi-balls-to-improve-boracay-wetland-s-water-quality>.

connection with other creations that lead to abuse, negligence and harmful actions towards other creations”.

The MORALS Ground Plan for Grade 7 entitled “Formation of Christian Conscience” is a class encounter for 1 session that runs for 50 minutes. This was made in ReEd 297.3 online class: *Readings in Moral Theology* under the supervision of Dr. Rachel Joyce Marie Sanchez. This ground plan aims to address the problem of the “students think that conscience is always right, not considering that it depends on how it was formed”. This was originally designed for Grade 9 students; with the light of Dr. Justin Joseph Badion, I revised the audience to Grade 7 so students will see the connection that being created by God as good, there are factors that would lead its fulfillment and that is the formation of Conscience. This will help deepen one’s understanding of the formation of conscience, there will be an integration of different scriptural texts, Church teachings, and daily experiences of the students. The teacher will also use discernment criterion to help students informed and enlightened that conscience is not something “automatic.” It is gradually shaped through all the many and complex factors that enter into our growth to Christian maturity (CFC 704).

The WORSHIP Ground Plan for Grade 7 entitled entitled “Care for the Common Home” is a paraliturgy for 50 minutes. This was made in ReEd297.4 online class: *Readings in Worship and Spirituality* under the supervision of Dr. Justin Joseph Badion. This paraliturgy is the culmination activity after the thorough discussion of Creation and Caring for God’s Creation. This ground plan aims to addresses the problem of the “the students simply do not care about their lifestyle and how it can affect the environment. They are not conscious of the materials they use. Every time they buy something, they are not aware that they are paying for its raw materials,

production costs and disposal as waste after use. Young people now also love to buy the latest gadgets, like mobile phones, computers, or laptops every one or two years.”

DOCTRINE GROUND PLAN

Topic: GOD CREATES AND SUSTAINS EVERYTHING THAT EXISTS

Audience: Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig

Problem: Students do not believe that they are innately good as a result they do not see their direct connection with non-human creations. This leads to abuse, negligence, and harmful actions toward non-human creations.

Type of Material: Instructional Materials

Session: 1 session - 55 minutes

CHRISTIAN MESSAGE	SOURCES	OBJECTIVES
<p>Doctrine: God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence. (CFC 339)</p> <p>Morals: We are called to imitate God our creator both in working and in loving our neighbors as we love ourselves and all non-human creations.</p> <p>Worship: In the offertory of the Mass, we pray with the priest: <i>“Blessed are you, Lord God of all creation, through your goodness we have this bread to offer, which earth has given and human hands have made.”</i></p>	<p>Sources:</p> <p>Sacred Scripture: -<i>Genesis 1:1-26, 28-31</i> In the beginning, God created the heavens and the earth. The earth was without form and empty; darkness covered the deep and the Spirit of the Lord moved over the waters...”</p> <p>-CFC 339 ...He is the God “who gives to all life and breath and everything else...In Him we live and move and have our being.” (Acts 17:25, 28)</p> <p>The <i>first personal aspect</i> of the doctrine of creation, then, is that God is creating, sustaining each of us in existence, now! “How could a thing remain, unless you willed it; or be preserved, had it not been called forth by You?”</p> <p>Means: Powerpoint presentation Worksheet 1</p>	<p>The lesson is ordered to enable the students to:</p> <p>Doctrine: explain that God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence;</p> <p>Morals: imitate God as our creator both in working and loving their neighbor as themselves and all non-human creations, and</p> <p>Worship: pray sincerely in thanking God for the gift of creation.</p>

<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (BEFORE)</p>	<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (DURING)</p>	<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (AFTER)</p>														
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The students know that God is the Creator. They have heard the creation story, but they do not understand that God is continually sustaining His creation in existence. ● Teenagers are experiencing challenges how to sustain their drives and motivations. ● Majority of the students are product of a broken family, where they believe that their parents gave birth to them but do not sustain their emotional and material needs. ● Most students who have parents abroad perceive that the responsibilities of their parents are only to sustain their needs due to long distance relationship. 	<p>Opening Prayer: “O God, we thank you for this earth, our home, for the wide sky and the blessed sun, for the salt sea and the running water, for the everlasting hills and the never-resting winds, for trees and the common grass underfoot. We thank you for our senses by which we hear the songs of birds, and see the splendor of the summer fields, and taste of the autumn fruits, and rejoice in the feel of the snow, and smell the breath of the spring. Grant us a heart wide open to all this beauty; and save our souls from being so blind that we pass unseeing when even the common thorn bush is aflame with your glory, O God our creator, who lives and reigns for ever and ever.”</p> <p>Motivation Question: Where does everything come from? Linking: Our automatic answer to this is God. Explain the purpose of each of God's creations and see if the purpose you see in them match what God had in mind.</p> <p><i>Worksheet 1</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="741 1106 1503 1372"> <thead> <tr> <th>Object/ Creations</th> <th>Purpose/s</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Light</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sky</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Water</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dry land</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Plants</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Trees</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Object/ Creations	Purpose/s	Light		Sky		Water		Dry land		Plants		Trees		<p>The students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● see God the Creator in a different and deeper light: recognizing Him both as creating and sustaining everything in existence. ● gain a deeper understanding of God’s creation. They now understand that it is not just a mere creation but also how God sustains everything. ● imitating God by exercising loving service by initiating outreach programs in helping the poor as an expression of working and loving their neighbors the way they love themselves and other advocacies that protect the non-human creations. ● dialogue prayerfully with God having an specific
Object/ Creations	Purpose/s															
Light																
Sky																
Water																
Dry land																
Plants																
Trees																

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most of the students believed that their own abilities, skills and knowledge are all their ways to sustain their existence, not of God. 	Sun/ Moon		<p>object that God created and what do God say and what is God's response</p>
	Day		
	Night		
	Animals		
	Humans		
	<p>Linking: All these creations are set by God to sustain the ecological balance. Through these creations, God continue to create and sustain the world.</p> <p>EXPOSITION: Genesis 1:1-26 : Creation Story The students assigned by the teacher before the class will read the Scripture passage aloud.</p> <p>Guide questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How did God create the earth and all that is in it? How does God see all His creation? What do these tell us about God and creation? <p>Expected answers to question no.3: God created everything with overflowing love. God sees it with beauty and goodness.</p> <p>Discussion: Reading closely at the presentation of creation, the Genesis narrative makes us see the wisdom, the goodness and the glory of God. We have seen clearly from the account of creation in Genesis the basic truths about the reality of all creation, everything that exists. We have noticed the beginning</p>		

of each creation as marked with a refrain-like verse, “evening came and morning followed,” reminding us that everything that we see around us has its origin, purpose and destiny. God is revealed in the story as the Origin and the Source of all that exist. **The Genesis narrative reveals that each creation, God has a purpose which gives meaning to its existence.**

Linking: God continually creates by being present and active in our daily lives. God provides us the support and guidance that we need every day.

1. “Para kanino ka bumabangon?” or “What do you both enjoy/love and are good at doing? What keeps you motivated to do what you do?”

2. What hinders you to see your purpose?

Expected Answers 2:

- Broken Family
- Parents working abroad
- Stressful workloads

These are hindrances for you not to see your purpose of why you continually exist. At times, you faced challenges that are heavy to bear, and would make you easily give up or want to stop living. More importantly, we should see what is beyond all these hindrances for us to encounter God. The God who is origin and source of goodness, who obviously, in His creative power, continues to create in sustaining everything in existence. We have seen the kind Creator-God we have: a God

	<p>of order, beauty, purpose, providence, wisdom. In taking delight in what He has done and is doing and taking a “rest,” we see a God not just of action, but of contemplation, relating lovingly in His very being, receiving glory in the fulfillment of the purpose for which He creates.</p> <p>-CFC 339 ...He is the God “who gives to all life and breath and everything else...In Him we live and move and have our being.” (Acts 17:25, 28)</p> <p>The <i>first personal aspect</i> of the doctrine of creation, then, is that God is creating, sustaining each of us in existence, now! “How could a thing remain, unless you willed it; or be preserved, had it not been called forth by You?”</p> <p>Morals Integration</p> <p>Being created, sustained by our Creator we should also do the same to His creations. God calls us to respect the goodness in His creation and the purpose for which He brings them into existence. This call includes our deep concern and be accountable in our action and to acknowledge that anything we do to – preserve, sustain, or destroy our Common Home will directly affect our lives most extensively experienced by the poor brothers and sisters.</p> <p>Guide Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cite concrete ways on how you take good care of God’s creation? ● How will these actions help our poor brothers and sisters? 	
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	<p>Possible answers for no. 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If trashes will be thrown in the proper bins, it will not clog drainage. This will not cause flood which urban poor will not experience. ● If there are a lot of trees, farmers crops will not be destroyed from the strong wind. <p>Processing: God called us to partake in caring for the rest of creations: human and non-human as it is stated in Genesis 1:26 <i>“Then God said: Let us make human beings in our image, after our likeness. Let them have dominion over the fish of the sea, the birds of the air, the tame animals, all the wild animals, and all the creatures that crawl on the earth.”</i> Since the human person is given dominion by God, it follows that we are responsible for the rest of creation that includes our responsibility towards our poor brothers and sisters who will be greatly affected with how we relate with the non-human creations. It is right that we initiate or join outreach programs or local projects that tangibly protect and preserve the environment and all life forms. This can be in a form of conducting seminars to raise awareness of environmental issues or tie up with LGUs in making Bokashi Balls or making waterlilies handicrafts by providing livelihood to the poor. Hence, God gives purpose to all creations and stewardship means beneficial to human and non-human to achieve mutual flourishing.</p>	
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	<p>Worship Integration God is honored and glorified whenever the goodness of His creation and the purpose for which He brings it into existence is acknowledged with a grateful heart.</p> <p>Pick a particular object created by God. Dialogue prayerfully with God having in mind this response to You?</p> <p>Evaluation: The teacher will ask the students to make a tagline of what they learned from the discussion.</p> <p>Summary: Creation will not remain in existence without God. All things would be lost without God’s continuing creativity, as going now (cf.CCC301). He will that all things He created should remain in existence. He is the God who gives to all life and breath and everything else.</p> <p>Closing Prayer: We pray sincerely the prayer used in Offertory: <i>“Blessed are you, Lord God of all creation, through your goodness we have this bread to offer, which earth has given and human hands have made.”</i></p>	
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MORALS GROUND PLAN

Topic: FORMATION OF CONSCIENCE

Audience: Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig

Problem: Students think that conscience is always right, not considering that it depends on how it was formed that will determine our relationship with ourselves, our neighbors and non-human creations.

Type of Material: Instructional Materials

Session: 1 session - 55 minutes

CHRISTIAN MESSAGE	SOURCES/MEANS/ASSESSMENTS	OBJECTIVES/LEARNING OUTCOMES
<p>MORALS: We are morally obliged to form and educate our consciences to be truly informed, mature, and truly Christian.</p> <p>DOCTRINE: God creates us with a capacity to know and love him, calls us to himself and writes his law on our hearts to help us draw closer to him. All of us have the personal responsibility to align our consciences with the truth.</p> <p>WORSHIP: Prayer helps us form our conscience to discern the moral good and develop a sense of responsibility in obeying God’s law.</p>	<p>SOURCES: SACRED SCRIPTURE: Romans 9:1. “I speak the truth in Christ: I do not lie. My conscience bears me witness in the Holy Spirit”</p> <p>CHURCH TEACHINGS: Church Teaching: Catechism for Filipino Catholics 707 Two types of formative factors, are stressed: 1) “heart” factors such as reading and reflecting on Jesus’ teaching and actions, and our affective prayer and sacramental life wherein we encounter the Risen Christ; and 2) “mind” factors __ attending “to the sacred and certain doctrine of the Church, whose duty is to authoritatively teach that Truth which is Christ himself, and also to declare and confirm those principles of the moral order which have their origin in human nature itself” (DH 14).</p>	<p>The lesson is ordered to enable the students to:</p> <p>MORALS: practice formative ways in forming the mind and heart to attain Christian conscience as they face choices everyday as they develop the sense of responsibility in obeying God’s law which includes loving the non-human creations.</p> <p>DOCTRINE: explain the importance of forming, educating, and shaping a correct Christian conscience</p>

	<p>Opus Dei -Topic 26: Freedom, Law and Conscience A right or true conscience refers to a conscience that judges truthfully regarding the moral quality of an act. An erroneous conscience fails to reach the truth, viewing as good an action that in reality is bad, or vice versa. The cause of an erroneous conscience is ignorance, which can be invincible (and blameless) if it dominates a person to such an extent that there is no possibility of recognizing it and amending it; this ignorance may also be vincible (or culpable) if a person can recognize and overcome it but fails to do so because he or she does not want to use the means available. [27] A culpably erroneous conscience does not excuse from sin and can actually aggravate it.</p> <p>PBC 154 par 3– Discernment Spiritual on Personal Level needs to be intensified in Catholic morality, conscience has always been presented as the ultimate instance for decision making. in this process of the formation of conscience – never definitively brought to a conclusion – the believer has the responsibility and the duty to confront personal discernment with that of those who are responsible for the community.”</p> <p>RESOURCES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opening Prayer ● Closing Prayer: “Open My Eyes” (https://prayer.knowing-jesus.com/Prayers-for-Discernment). 	<p>WORSHIP: pray unceasingly to God as they continue to search the moral good and in result knowing His will.</p>
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	<p>MEANS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pair-Think-Share ● Collaborative Learning Group ● Class Discussion ● Article Analysis: <i>Greta Thunberg: The World's Youthful Climate Conscience</i> <p>ASSESSMENTS</p> <p>Formative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Let's Look Back ● Compare and Contrast – Personal Practices vs Christian Ways in Forming -Mind and Hearts <p>Summative assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Article Analysis 					
<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (BEFORE)</p>	<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (DURING)</p>	<p>HUMAN EXPERIENCE (AFTER)</p>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Some students are expose to social media where they have access to all information suitable or not suitable to their age ● Some students live with their separated parents who have different families ● Some students are comfortable sharing their problems, principles, like and dislikes with their peers than their parents 	<p>The session will start with an Opening Prayer.</p> <p>Motivation: Let's Look Back</p> <p>Think-Pair-Share</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The students will individually recall decisions that they made in the past by completing the tables below. <table border="1" data-bbox="689 1082 1523 1375"> <tr> <td data-bbox="689 1082 902 1375"> What was your happy decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i> </td> <td data-bbox="902 1082 1133 1375"> What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations) </td> <td data-bbox="1133 1082 1319 1375"> What is/are the effect/s? </td> <td data-bbox="1319 1082 1523 1375"> If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why? </td> </tr> </table>	What was your happy decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i>	What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations)	What is/are the effect/s?	If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why?	<p>The students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● practice conscious efforts in forming their mind and heart factors as their moral obligation to attain Christian conscience. ● gain deeper knowledge that conscience is continually developed as they continue with their countless interactions with the people around them. ● reassess factors and effects of their decisions by
What was your happy decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i>	What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations)	What is/are the effect/s?	If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why?			

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other students believe that conscience is always good and is always right, not considering that it depends on how it is formed • Some students look up to celebrities as their moral compass and in shaping their identity • Other students actively attend school religious activities and rituals while some diligently participate with their families’ religious practices such as praying the rosary and novenas • Often times, the students simply do not care about their lifestyle and how it can affect the environment. They are not conscious on the materials they use. Every time they buy something, they are not aware that they are paying for its raw materials, production costs and disposal as waste after use. Young people now also love to buy the latest 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="696 333 902 627"> What was your sad decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i> </td> <td data-bbox="911 333 1128 627"> What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations) </td> <td data-bbox="1137 333 1317 627"> What is/are the effect/s? </td> <td data-bbox="1326 333 1512 627"> If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why? </td> </tr> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </table>				What was your sad decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i>	What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations)	What is/are the effect/s?	If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why?					<p>aligning it with Christian forming of heart and mind.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • appreciate the value of prayer as their guide to know what is good and right for their decision making.
	What was your sad decision? <i>Explain in detailed using 5 sentences.</i>	What factors did you consider when you made that decision? (self, neighbors and non-human creations)	What is/are the effect/s?	If you could bring back the time, would you make the same decision? Why?									
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After 5 minutes, the students will share their answer with their partner. • The teacher will process that there were wrong decisions that were made because the judgement of conscience is wrong. <p>Linking: Oftentimes, people associate happy decision as good and sad decision as bad. This can be correct at times; however, formation of conscience is not about feelings but a moral judgement using good and sound reasoning.</p> <p>EXPOSITION: Sacred Scripture: “I speak the truth in Christ: I do not lie. My conscience bears me witness in the Holy Spirit” Romans 9:1 Church Teaching: Catechism for Filipino Catholics 707 The teacher will discuss and expound the Church Teaching.</p>													

gadgets, like mobile phones, computers, or laptops every one or two years.

Opus Dei -Topic 26: Freedom, Law and Conscience
 The teacher will integrate this source to be aware of the existence of error judgement.

FORMATION OF CONSCIENCE
 The students will be asked to list down their practices in forming their hearts and minds.

Ways of forming the HEART	Ways of forming the MIND

Compare and Contrast:

- When the students are done, the teacher will show the list of Christian ways in forming the two formative factors -heart and mind factors.
- The students will compare their personal practices to the Christian ways of forming the heart and mind.
- The teacher will also discuss that formation of one’s conscience depends on our countless interactions with parents, guardians, relatives, friends, and other members of the community. Two types of formative factors: **“heart” factors** such as reading and reflecting on Jesus’ teaching and actions, and our affective prayer and sacramental life wherein we encounter the Risen Christ (CFC 707, 726); and **“mind” factors** (CFC 707, 726)

	<p>such as attending to the sacred and certain doctrine of the Church, whose duty is to authoritatively teach that Truth which is Christ himself, and also to declare and confirm those principles of the moral order which have their origin in human nature itself (DH 14). Ecological aspect will be seen in both formative factors in which learning in school and doing research in the awareness of the human impact on the environment and other non-human creations which needs for humans to adjust their behaviors and thinking to ensure that the environment and its resources are not destroyed.</p> <p>PBC – Discernment: Spiritual in Personal level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students will be reminded that when the circumstances of life challenge us with difficult choices, we become more aware of the need to form a right conscience. 1 among the 3 markers of essential to making sound and good decisions which is Spiritual in Personal level <i>“needs to be intensified in Catholic morality, conscience has always been presented as the ultimate instance for decision making. in this process of the formation of conscience – never definitively brought to a conclusion – the believer has the responsibility and the duty to confront personal discernment with that of those who are responsible for the community.” (154 par.3)</i> 	
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	<p>INTEGRATION:</p> <p>Article Analysis Greta Thunberg: The World's Youthful Climate Conscience By Helene Dauschy And Tom Little</p> <p>Swedish climate activist and global star Greta Thunberg understood climate change at an early age and has rallied youths around the world and parents to her cause, sparking criticism along the way. In less than a year the now 16-year-old's humble "climate strike" has become a global movement and set her up as a potential 2019 Nobel Peace Prize laureate. As her strict climate ethos prevents her from flying she is preparing to travel to the New York UN Climate Summit on September 23 by sailboat. Thunberg's climate struggle began quietly in August 2018 when she skipped school for the first three weeks, and then on Fridays to spend the day outside Sweden's parliament with a sign labelled "School strike for climate".</p> <p>Swedish media, at the time occupied by upcoming parliamentary elections, didn't pay much attention to the young girl's message, but only at first. Since then Greta, most often seen wearing her hair in tightly knit braids, has diligently continued her weekly protest until recently. "I'm planning to continue until Sweden is in line with the Paris agreement and that might take a while," she told AFP TV in late 2018. Her demands have attracted attention and she has been asked to address global leaders, and adorned the cover of international magazines such as Time and Vogue.</p>	
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Swedish climate campaigner Greta Thunberg launched a campaign that has echoed among young people worldwide. Around the world, young activists have heard the call and modelled protests of their own after Greta's, leading to both praise and criticism. "We are after all just children. You don't have to listen to us," she said during a speech to France's National Assembly in July, responding to some of her critics, who had dismissed her as a "prophetess in shorts" and the "Justin Bieber of ecology".

Source: <https://phys.org/news/2019-08-greta-thunberg-world-youthful-climate.html> accessed March 25, 2023

- The students will read and analyze the news article.
- The students will individually answer the questions in the table below:

If you are Greta, would you do the same? Why? Why not?	What are the factors that you consider in answering the 1 st column?	What will be the possible effect/s of such decision?

- After 5 minutes, the student will be asked to go to her group to share her/his answer.
- The group will come up with the answer to this question:

How would a person who has Christian conscience object to the climate crisis that greatly affected our poor brothers and sisters?

- The teacher will process that there are factors to consider in making decision in a particular situation that

	<p>promote ecological justice both for the environment and marginalized communities. This means that there is a need to discern to reach a Christian religious conscience. <u>Discernment</u> helps in reassessing the factors and effects of their decisions and aligning it with the 2 Christian formative factors- heart and mind.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Discerning is a process and prayer helps in the process of searching the truth. The student will compose a 1 sentence prayer to ask God's guidance in knowing the truth. <p>The session will end with the closing prayer "Open My Eyes".</p>	
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WORSHIP GROUND PLAN

Topic: CARE FOR OUR COMMON HOME

Audience: Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig

Problem: To take accountability in taking care of God's creation as one of the social responsibilities. The teacher uses the 4 elements to intensify in valuing the commitment to caring the common home to exemplify one's purpose, value and meaning in life.

Type of Material: Paraliturgy

Session: 1 session - 55 minutes

CHRISTIAN MESSAGE	SOURCES/MEANS/ASSESSMENTS	OBJECTIVES/LEARNING OUTCOMES
<p>WORSHIP: The value and purpose of all creation is ultimately for the adoration of the Creator.</p> <p>DOCTRINE: Everything that God created is good. From this truth comes the ultimate meaning, purpose, and destiny of all people and of the rest of creation.</p> <p>MORALS: We are called to respect one another in words and in actions, having been created in God's image and likeness.</p>	<p>SOURCES: SACRED SCRIPTURES: 1 Corinthians 3:13 ...the work of each will come to light, for the Day* will disclose it. It will be revealed with fire, and the fire [itself] will test the quality of each one's work.</p> <p>Genesis 1:6-7 Then God said: Let there be a dome in the middle of the waters, to separate one body of water from the other. God made the dome,* and it separated the water below the dome from the water above the dome. And so it happened.</p> <p>Genesis 1:30 and to all the wild animals, all the birds of the air, and all the living creatures that crawl on the earth, I give all the green plants for food. And so it happened.</p>	<p>The lesson is ordered to enable the students to:</p> <p>WORSHIP: profess the truth that we are creatures who owe our Creator adoration.</p> <p>DOCTRINE: explain that God's creation -human and non-humans are special and good because of the ultimate meaning, purpose and destiny.</p> <p>MORALS: assess the consequences of their actions and commit to social responsibilities to fulfill stewards of God's creation</p>

	<p>Psalm 24:1 The earth is the LORD's and all it holds, the world and those who dwell in it.</p> <p>CHURCH TEACHINGS: Catechism of the Catholic Church 291 "In the beginning was the Word. . . and the Word was God. . . all things were made through him, and without him was not anything made that was made."129 The New Testament reveals that God created everything by the eternal Word, his beloved Son. In him "all things were created, in heaven and on earth. . . all things were created through him and for him. He is before all things, and in him all things hold together."130 The Church's faith likewise confesses the creative action of the Holy Spirit, the "giver of life", "the Creator Spirit" (Veni, Creator Spiritus), the "source of every good".131</p> <p>Catechism of the Catholic Church 344 There is a solidarity among all creatures arising from the fact that all have the same Creator and are all ordered to his glory: May you be praised, O Lord, in all your creatures, especially brother sun, by whom you give us light for the day; he is beautiful, radiating great splendour, and offering us a symbol of you, the Most High. . . May you be praised, my Lord, for sister water, who is very useful and humble, precious and chaste. May you be praised, my Lord, for sister earth, our mother, who bears and feeds us, and produces the variety of fruits and dappled flowers and grasses. . . Praise and bless my Lord, give thanks and serve him in all humility.212</p>	
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	<p>Catechism of the Catholic Church 282 Catechesis on creation is of major importance. It concerns the very foundations of human and Christian life: for it makes explicit the response of the Christian faith to the basic question that men of all times have asked themselves: 120 "Where do we come from?" "Where are we going?" "What is our origin?" "What is our end?" "Where does everything that exists come from and where is it going?" the two questions, the first about the origin and the second about the end, are inseparable. They are decisive for the meaning and orientation of our life and actions.</p> <p>Catechism of the Catholic Church 290 "In the beginning God created the heavens and the earth":128 three things are affirmed in these first words of Scripture: the eternal God gave a beginning to all that exists outside of himself; he alone is Creator (the verb "create" - Hebrew bara - always has God for its subject). the totality of what exists (expressed by the formula "the heavens and the earth") depends on the One who gives it being.</p> <p>Laudatu Si 243. At the end, we will find ourselves face to face with the infinite beauty of God (cf. <i>1 Cor</i> 13:12), and be able to read with admiration and happiness the mystery of the universe, which with us will share in unending plenitude. Even now we are journeying towards the sabbath of eternity, the new Jerusalem, towards our common home in heaven. Jesus says: "I make all things new" (<i>Rev</i> 21:5). Eternal life will be a shared experience of awe, in which each creature, resplendently transfigured, will take its rightful place and have something to give those poor men and women who will have been liberated once and for all.</p>	
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	<p>244. In the meantime, we come together to take charge of this home which has been entrusted to us, knowing that all the good which exists here will be taken up into the heavenly feast. In union with all creatures, we journey through this land seeking God, for “if the world has a beginning and if it has been created, we must enquire who gave it this beginning, and who was its Creator”.^[172] Let us sing as we go. May our struggles and our concern for this planet never take away the joy of our hope.</p> <p>RESOURCES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opening Prayer- Season of Creation 2020 - Jubilee for the Earth (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=09ojKLEKD68&t=28s) ● Peace Poll Garden/ St. Francis of Assisi Garden (<i>If the weather will not permit, the students may do it in the classroom. They may also assign station for each element</i>) ● Four Elements: Earth- Soil and potted plants Fire- candles Water- clean water and basin with dirty water Wind- electric fan ● Fire - The environmental impact of wildfires and climate change's role https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IoYJbcWcVzg ● Water - Why Care About Water? National Geographic (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fvkzjt3b-dU) ● Air – Air Pollution 101 – (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e6rglsLy1Ys) ● Earth - Earth 101- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HCDVN7DCzYE 	
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closing Prayer- A Christian prayer in union with creation - https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/encyclicals/documents/papa-francesco_20150524_encyclica-laudato-si.html <p>MEANS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Playing of Gong, Commitment Statement, Videos, Listening to Music, Collaborative Learning Group, Symbolism, Reflection <p>ASSESSMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commitment Statement 	
HUMAN EXPERIENCE (BEFORE)	HUMAN EXPERIENCE (DURING)	HUMAN EXPERIENCE (AFTER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some students do not engage in the choices of markets of their families, that they just simply buy in supermarkets what normally people buy in local market. Some students waste food and do not care about buying materials with disposable packaging. Some families simply use their cars for convenience, whether or not their destination is just near or accessible 	<p>The session will start with an opening prayer.</p> <p>Motivation: Group leader will offer the symbols of their assigned element and place it in their station. From the center of the garden, the student will walk towards the grotto of Saint Francis of Assisi. That would be the start of the station.</p> <p>EXPOSITION <u>FIRE</u> <i>The group leader will light the candles.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Video: The student will play the video showing the reality of fire. <p>Video Title- "<u>The environmental impact of wildfires and climate change's role</u>"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scriptural Reading- 1 Corinthians 3:13 Points to reflect: Catechism of the Catholic Church 291 – Fire aside from being the important element, it is also 	<p>The students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> promote sustainable consumption by buying ecological and fair-trade goods as a way of supporting local farmers reduce food waste and avoid single-use materials promote climate-friendly mobility like riding bicycle, telling parents to install carpooling or car-sharing systems, and walking when going to nearby places reflect on how their lifestyles affect the environment and commit to

<p>through walking or biking.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reflect on how their lifestyles affect the environment and commit to more sustainable ways of living • some families diligently participate in Earth Hour as their way to support care for creation 	<p>associated with the Holy Spirit, "giver of life", "the Creator Spirit" (Veni, Creator Spiritus), the "source of every good".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection question: “What are practices that you knew are wrong our common home but you continue to resist the Holy Spirit to correct your wrong doings?” <p><u>WATER</u> <i>The group leader will pour the clean water to the garden waterfalls. The basin with dirty water will also be shown to the students. They will be invited to compare the water from the garden waterfalls with the dirty water.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video: The student will play the video showing the reality of fire. <p>Video Title- Why Care About Water? National Geographic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scriptural Reading: Genesis 1:6-7 • Points to reflect: Catechism of the Catholic Church 344 – Water is very useful and the basis of life. We need to adhere to the call of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals # 6 which is to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. • Reflection question: When did you appreciate your easy access to water? <p><u>AIR</u> <i>The group leader will turn on the electric fan and invite everyone to compare when the fan was not on.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video: The student will play the video showing the reality of fire. <p>Video Title- Air Pollution 101</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scriptural Reading: Genesis 1:30 	<p>more sustainable ways of living</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • initiate Earth hour at home • consciously conserve energy by turning off lights, use glass of water when brushing teeth and do urban gardening
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Points to reflect: Catechism of the Catholic Church 282 – The breath of life can be associated with air. It is important course of our life and action. ● Reflection question: Do you appreciate your breathing? <p><u>EARTH</u></p> <p><i>The group leader will remove the potted plants from the pot and plant it in the soil of the garden. She will invite everyone to scoop up soil and put it in the plant.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Video: The student will play the video showing the reality of fire. <p>Video Title- Earth 101</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scriptural Reading: Psalm 24:1 ● Points to reflect: Catechism of the Catholic Church 290 – Earth is our common home that is given to us, so we exist with purpose and meaning. Earth supports life. ● Reflection question: How does earth supports your purpose in life? <p>INTEGRATION</p> <p>Prayers of the Faithful: (Laudatu Si 243-244)</p> <p>In every petition, let the prayer be: Lord, let our struggles and our concern for this planet never take away the joy of our hope.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. May Pope Francis and Church leaders, advocate care for mother earth and continue to seek ways for sustainable goals. <i>Let us pray to the Lord.</i> 2. May the government leaders call attention to the causes and consequences of environmental degradation and enlist others 	
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	<p>to assist in programs that can preserve, protect, and sustain. <i>Let us pray to the Lord.</i></p> <p>3. May families willingly share responsibilities, support and participate actively in fostering care for creation. <i>Let us pray to the Lord.</i></p> <p>4. May everyone contribute their time, heartfelt attention, abilities, and resources in directly resolving environment issues at home, school and community. <i>Let us pray to the Lord.</i></p> <p>Commitment Statement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All students will write in a colored paper their commitment statement in taking concrete steps on how they will show their social responsibility as stewards of God’s creation. ● Students will post their commitment statement in the Peace Polls. <p>Closing Prayer- “A Christian Prayer in Union with Creation”</p>	
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CHAPTER IV

METHODOLOGY

Methods based on the “Good News”—“based from the law of three fidelities as outlined by the NCDP- fidelity to God, fidelity to man, and the fidelity to the Church, the Pedagogy of Faith for Filipinos Today follows three basic catechetical principles: integration, inculturation, and community forming.”¹

INTEGRATION

“Integration, as the first principle of catechetical methodology, refers to the holistic, unified character of all authentic catechesis.”² This is with one basic goal: to bring the good News into the totality of the person’s being involving the head, heart and hands.

LIFE INTEGRATION

Life integration is “to effectively bring the total inspiring message of Christ into the minds, wills and hearts of today’s Filipino.”³ Using CFCs pattern of catechism, part of the “Context which focuses the topic within our specific Filipino situation, with its particular problems, attitudes, values, and weaknesses.”⁴ This is seen in the Human

¹ *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines*, para. 355.

² *Ibid.*, para. 356.

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ Catholic Bishops’ Conference of the Philippines, *Catechism for Filipino Catholics*, para. 23.

Experiences: Before, During and After. The Human Experience During is an attempt to deliver the Christian Message in a step-by-step process.

In the Doctrine Ground Plan entitled “God Creates and Sustains Everything that Exists,” Human Experience Before generally states that students only perceive creation as something that is already done which is contrasting that God sustains all His creations. This is also visible in their respective context such as broken family, distant parents where they see that parents are there to merely provide their physical needs. This perspective affects notion with God as merely Creator and not sustainer. In Human Experience During, consist of activities elaborating all God created and the purpose of each. Student is also asked a simple question “*Para kanino ka bumabangon?*” yet demands a deeper answer. Their answer also will be critique with the follow-up question: “What hinders you to see your purpose” leads now to their present situation stated in Human Experience Before. Using the Church Teaching CFC 339 to process their answers that “God is creating, sustaining each of us in existence, now!” The Human Experience After, aspire to see God in everything and how God sustains his creations as an ongoing process of creating. This part also tangibly connects God in all things that exist, seeing Him as sustainer and giver of purpose.

In the Morals Ground Plan entitled “Formation of the Christian Conscience,” Human Experience Before mentioned that students believed that conscience is always right, social media influencers and celebrities served as their moral compass and some students are influenced spiritually and religiously by their parents. For Human Experience During, students will be asked to reflect on their happy and sad decisions, the factors that they consider when they decide, effects and asked to reflect if they could bring back time, will they make the same decisions. The teacher will process the there were wrong decisions that were made because the judgement of conscience is wrong.

Using the Church Teaching, Opus Dei on the topic of “Freedom, Law and Conscience” the teacher will directly emphasize the existence of error judgments. The students will be asked to list down their practices in forming their hearts and minds for five minutes. Once they are done, they need to compare and contrast their personal answers with the Christian ways in forming the heart and mind. The student will analyzed some articles and distinguish factors that will be considered in making decisions. The session will end with a 1-sentence prayer composition in asking God’s guidance in knowing the truth. In the Human Experience After, hope to enforce that in forming Christian conscience it needs a conscious efforts in forming the heart and mind factors these includes the countless interactions with the people around them and to value prayer as their guide in knowing the truth in making right and good decisions.

In the Worship Ground Plan entitled “Care for our Common Home”, Human Experience Before showed that most of them are not engaged in their families’ practices in buying, using and recycling materials. For Human Experience During, each element will be seen through the materials provided by each group, a video will be shown to portray the reality of the element and in the reflection question of each element, they are asked to delve into their personal participation in caring for the common home. Their admittance to their negligence and unaccountability will lead them to realize that their simple action has an effect on the total condition of our Common Home. The Human Experience After hope to promote sustainable consumption by buying ecological to attain conscious efforts in alleviating negative practices in their lifestyles as a being a steward of God’s creation.

STRUCTURAL INTEGRATION

Structural Integration is “showing the distinction yet intrinsic relationship between the three essential components of the faith: doctrine (Creed), morals (Commandments/ virtues), and Worship (prayer/ sacraments).”⁵ The integration of Word, Witness and Worship to have a sound and effective catechetical method which can also be seen in the programs, class, or curriculum. This is the attempt to remind students that the lesson is connected to other topics. The topics that will be discussed after the Doctrine Ground Plan on “God Creates and Sustains Everything That Exists” are Human Dignity and Freedom. These topics will be followed by the Morals Ground Plan Topic on “Formation of Conscience” and discussion on Caring God’s Creation. Lastly, the Worship Ground Plan is a paraliturgy on “Care for Our Common Home.” This is evident in the interrelation on how the Christian Message and Objectives are formulated.

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, the Christian Message focuses on Doctrine component that “God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence” (CFC 339). This points to the truth that God continually creates and sustains all His creations. In the Morals component, “We are called to imitate God our Creator both in working and loving our neighbors as we love ourselves and all non-human creations” which points to the truth that God continues to create, He also calls all His creations to be like Him. Initiating outreaches in helping the poor as an expression in loving their neighbors and supporting advocacies that protect the non-human creations are activities that Grade 7 students love to do. In all these, Worship components focuses on giving glory to God through the prayer during the Offertory part of the Eucharistic celebration: “*Blessed are*

⁵ *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines*, para. 357.

you, Lord God of all creation, through your goodness we have this bread to offer, which earth has given and human hands have made". In structural integration, all the three components are aligned and will be attained in the Objectives part. In the Doctrine objectives "explain that God is creating and sustaining of us in existence" while in Morals objectives, "imitate God as our creator both in working and loving their neighbor as themselves and all non-human creations" and for Worship objectives "pray sincerely in thanking God for the gift of creation."

In the MORALS Ground Plan, the Christian Message stresses Morals component "we are morally obliged to form and educate our consciences to be truly informed, mature, and truly Christian." This will be attained in Morals Objective to "practice formative ways in forming the mind and heart to attain Christian conscience as they face choices everyday as they develop the sense of responsibility in obeying God's law which includes loving the non-human creations." There is a clear connection between the two- the obligation to attain Christian Conscience is to practice everyday the formative ways in forming the two factors: mind and heart. In the Christian Message Doctrine component, "God creates us with a capacity to know and love him, calls us to himself and writes his law on our hearts to help us draw closer to him. All of us have the personal responsibility to align our consciences with the truth." This will be attained in Doctrine Objectives, "explain the importance of forming, educating, and shaping a correct Christian conscience." In the Christian Message Worship component, "prayer helps us to form our conscience to discern the moral good and develop a sense of responsibility in obeying God's law" which will be attained in Worship objectives, "pray unceasingly to God as they continue to search the moral good and in result knowing His will."

In the WORSHIP Ground Plan, the Christian Message is to highlight that value and purpose of all creation's existence is ultimately adoring the Creator which comes from the scripture passage of Psalm, "I praise you, because I am wonderfully made; wonderful are your works! My very self you know."⁶ The Doctrine component emphasizes the beautiful truth that all God's creations are good where the meaning, purpose and destiny are deeply rooted. The Moral component demands that human beings must take good care of God's creation. The Christian Message will come to its fruition through the Objectives. The objectives in the Worship component shows the adoration to God professing the truth in the scriptural readings and points to reflect in each element. The objectives in the Doctrine component expressed in the Prayers of the Faithful is elaborated to target "human beings are special and good because God created us and is continually creating us in His image and likeness." The Morals component shows that the video analysis part caters the actual reality of the element which aspires them to resolve the problem, and the commitment statement demands them to fulfill stewardship.

DIMENSION INTEGRATION

This integration "refers to the process of integrating multiple dimensions within each other of the three components of faith – Doctrine, Morals and Worship."⁷

Doctrine Dimension Integration

Doctrine component across the three Ground Plans are: a) God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence, b) "God creates us with a capacity to know and love

⁶ Psalm 139:14

⁷ *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines*, para. 358.

him, calls us to himself and writes his law on our hearts to help us draw closer to him. All of us have the personal responsibility to align our consciences with the truth”; and c) “Everything that God created is good. From this truth comes the ultimate meaning, purpose, and destiny of all people and of the rest of creation.”

The first part is seen in the Doctrine Ground Plan—Doctrine Integration part which uses the Creation Story to see the wisdom, the goodness and the glory of God. There is a highlight of the refrain-like verse, “evening came and morning followed,” reminding that we see around us has its origin, purpose and destiny. The Genesis narrative reveals that each creation, God has a purpose which gives meaning to its existence. The second part is seen in the Morals Ground Plan—Doctrine Integration part in which the teacher will elaborate and explain that there is an existence of error judgment and it is right to know the ways to form the heart and the mind to come up with a Christian conscience. In the Worship Ground Plan—Doctrine Integration part is seen in the first part of each presentation of the element during the para-liturgy. Across the three Ground Plans there is a clear connection that God created all His creations good and that He continues to create and sustain them. Seeking truth through God to form conscience to love the good and avoid evil.

Morals Dimension Integration

Morals component across the three Ground Plans are: a) “we are called to imitate God our Creator both in working and loving our neighbors as we love ourselves and non-human creations”; b) “we are morally obliged to form and educate our consciences to be truly informed, mature, and truly Christian”; and c) “we are called to respect one another in words and in actions, having been created in God’s image and likeness”.

The first part is seen in the Doctrine Ground Plan—Morals Integration part which highlights that being created, sustained by our Creator we should also do the same to His creations. God calls us to respect the goodness in His creation and the purpose for which He brings them into existence. The students will be asked to answer the question: “What are some ways by which you show appreciation and respect for God’s creation?” The second part is seen in Morals Ground Plan – Morals Integration part which uses news article to critique and figure out factors and effects in the decisions made. The last part is seen in the Worship Ground Plan – Worship Integration part which is seen in the presentation of each element where students need to answer the reflection questions: Fire Element—“What practices that you knew are wrong in our common home but you continue to resist the Holy Spirit to correct your wrong doings?”; Water Element—“When did you appreciate your easy access to water?”; Air Element—“Do you appreciate your breathing?” and Earth Element—“How does earth supports your purpose in life?”

Worship Dimension Integration

Worship component across the three Ground Plans are : a) “In the offertory of the Mass, we pray with the priest: “Blessed are you, Lord God of all creation, through your goodness we have this bread to offer, which earth has given and human hands have made”; b) “Prayer helps us form our conscience to discern the moral good and develop a sense of responsibility in obeying God’s law”; and c) “The value and purpose of all creation is ultimately for the adoration of the Creator.”

The first part is seen in the Doctrine Ground Plan—Worship integration part which highlights God who is honored and glorified whenever the goodness of His creation and the purpose for which He brings it into existence is acknowledged with a

grateful heart. This is seen in the activity where students will pick a particular object created by God and they need to prayerfully dialogue with Him, imagining His response as well. The second part is seen in the Morals Ground Plan- Worship Integration part which highlights discernment as a process and prayer that helps in the process of searching the truth. The student will compose a 1-sentence prayer to ask God's guidance in knowing the truth. The third part is seen in the Worship Ground Plan—Worship Integration part which is presented in an adoration of God through para-liturgy as a way of embracing the truths that God. It is through prayer that we express our state of capabilities and incapacities and to humbly ask God to work in the midst. This is seen in the “Prayers of the Faithful” prayer: “Lord, let our struggles and our concern for this planet never take away the joy of our hope” as clear manifestation that bringing some concerns to God shows humility of the incapability.

SOURCE INTEGRATION

Source Integration “aims at such a unified, creative use of the primary sources that is faithful both to God’s revelation and to the human factors involved in catechesis.”⁸ Scripture, Tradition and Human Experience as primary sources of catechesis must be used creatively and adapted to the concrete catechesis being carried on. This is seen in Sources and Means: Sacred Scripture, Church Teachings, Resources and how it manifested in the Human Experience During.

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, the sources used are as follows: Genesis 1:1-26, 28-31 while in Tradition: CFC 339 and Human Experience During are worksheet activity, discussion, reflection questions and tagline making.

⁸ Ibid., para. 359.

Guided by the Objectives especially by the Doctrine objective, “explain that God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence,” the source integration is displayed. Beginning with a question: “Where does everything come from?” that leads to answering the Worksheet 1 where students will personally elaborate the purpose of each object and critique if the object’s purpose are in accordance with what God intended for it. Narration of the Creation Story will follow and the teacher will discuss and emphasize that each creation has given a purpose by God which gives meaning to its purpose. Students will be asked a simple question: “*Para kanino ka bumabangon?*” or “What do you both enjoy/love and are good at doing? What keeps you motivated to do what you do?” and “What hinders you to see your purpose?” The teacher will process the students answers by validating all the factors that hinders them to see their purpose and highlighting that God in His creative power, continues to create in sustaining everything in existence with the support of Church teaching CFC 339.

In the Morals Ground Plan, the sources are Romans 9:1 while in Tradition: CFC 707 and Opus Dei on Topic 26: Freedom, Law and Conscience and Human Experience During are Think-Pair-Share, Collaborative Learning Group, Class Discussion, Compare and Contrast and Article Analysis.

In the Moral Objective “we are morally obliged to form and educate our consciences to be truly informed, mature and truly Christian” is achieved through the sources. This is most evident in the Exposition of the Sacred Scripture: Romans 9:1 intensified by CFC 707 stressing the two types of formative factors which leads to an activity: Compare and Contrast Activity where students will list down their personal practices in forming their hearts and minds. The teacher will discuss the Christian ways of forming the heart and the mind and the students will compare their personal practices with the Christian ways. Ecological aspect will also be seen in both formative factors

in which learning in school and doing research in the awareness of the human impact on the environment and other non-human creations which needs for humans to adjust their behaviors and thinking to ensure that the environment and its resources are not destroyed.

In the Worship Ground Plan, the sources are: 1 Corinthians 3:13, Genesis 1:6-7, Genesis 1:30 and Psalm 24:1 while in Tradition: CFC, CCC and Laudatu Si and Human Experience During such as playing of gong, scripture reading, video analysis, reflection, symbolism and commitment statement.

In its objectives especially in worship objective, “profess the truth that we are creatures who owe our Creator adoration” directs the integration of its sources. The scriptures are appropriate for the elements; a) Fire element—the scripture is from 1 Corinthians 3:13 to associate fire with the “Holy Spirit”; b) Water element—the scripture is from Genesis 1:6-7 to put emphasis that in the creative days, God placed the water below so people will have an easy access to it, as it is the basis of life; c) Air element—the scripture is from Genesis 1:30 with the support of CCC 282 to put emphasis that the breath of life can be associated with air; d) Earth element—the scripture is from Psalm 24:1 that is intensified with CCC 290 pointing that Earth is our common home that is given to us, so we exist with purpose and meaning. Human Experience (especially the witnessing of the symbolism of all elements- candle, water, electric fan, potted plants and soil) brings out the context and learning.

SUBJECT INTEGRATION

This integration “focuses on how those being catechized actually assimilate and interiorize the catechetical instructions being given them. The catechist must “get in the

shoes” of the catechized and speak to them directly, clearly, in a way they can understand, imbibe, and make their own the particular content of catechesis.”⁹ This integration gives a clear picture of the believer. This is seen in Human Experience: Before and After. Human Experience (Before) shows the multifaceted situation and context of the students that serves as the anchor on how to make the Christian message be known in the process of Human Experience (During) while Human Experience (After) elaborates the becoming or the hope that has been transpired.

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, a 55-minute academic lesson to be given to Grade 7 students. The context of the students especially on seeing God as Creator is stated in Human Experience (Before). The first point is merely seeing Him as the Creator whose task is done in the past and has nothing to do in the present. The second point is on the thrive of students who encounter the challenges of the early teenage years. Then, the 3rd and 4th points highlight the family situation of the students who are facing the effects of broken family, single parents or distant parents whose work are away from home. Lastly, the 5th point dwells in the student’s perception on their abilities, skills and talents that are developed, nourished and nurtured in their own connoting the absence of God as the one who sustains all these.

Aligning the Human Experience (After), on the first two points on recognizing God the Creator who sustains and creates will be seen in the Human Experience (During) when the teacher would ask students to elaborate the purpose of God’s creations. It follows with the activities where they would point out the hindrances in seeing their purpose but God continues to reveal Himself who gives meaning in each creation. The third point mentioned in the Human Experience (After) is imitating God

⁹ Ibid., para. 360.

by exercising loving service by initiating outreach programs that can help levied the lives of others especially the poor and promoting advocacies that protect the non-human creations which will be seen in the discussion where the teacher would ask students to answer the question: “What are some ways by which you show appreciation of and respect for God’s creation?” The last point mentioned in the Human Experience (After) is to dialogue prayerfully with God having a specific object that God created what do God say and what is God’s response to it which will be seen in the composition of prayerful dialogue with the created object by God.

In the Morals Ground Plan, a 50-minute academic lesson to be given to Grade 7 students. The context of the students especially on the underlying factors of their formation of conscience lies in the Human Experience (Before). The first point is the accessibility of the social media that offers a lot of information that most are not suitable for their ages. The second point is the situation of the families whose parents are separated. The 3rd point is the role of their friends in the formation of their conscience and the 4th point is still the misconception of the students towards conscience despite of the discussion prior to this lesson. The 5th point draws the idols of the Grade 7 students whom they look up to which serve as their moral compass. The sixth point are the religious practices and rituals that students are particular with their involvement since they see these in their families. Lastly, the 7th point are the current ecological lifestyles that affect their conscience.

Aligning this in the Human Experience (After), on the first point, student will practice conscious efforts in forming their mind and heart factors as their moral obligation to attain Christian conscience through an individual activity recalling decisions they made in the past so they can determine factors that generally affect their decisions and action and, assess the consequences they produce. The second point

which states that students will gain deeper knowledge that conscience is continually developed as they continue with their countless interactions with the people around them which is seen in the entire discussion especially in the activity where students list down their practices in forming their hearts and minds. On the third point, reassess factors and effects of their decisions by aligning it with Christian forming of heart and mind which will be seen in the article analysis. The last point where students appreciate the value of prayer as their guide to know what is good and right for their decision making which is seen in the closing activity where students will compose a 1 sentence prayer to ask God's guidance in knowing the truth.

In the WORSHIP Ground Plan, a 50-minute prayer period intended to Grade 7 students, the context of the students in the Human Experience (Before) provided us an idea that their lifestyle is not aligned with being stewards of God's creation which connects to the following points: (1) no engagement in choices of markets; (2) buys food from grab or delivery apps which most food are in disposable packaging; (3) some families used cars most of the time regardless of the distance. While the fourth and fifth points are mostly from students who reflect on their lifestyles and support the ways on caring the Earth by participating in the Earth Hour.

Aligning this in the Human Experience (After), on the first two points, students will support farmers as their way in promoting sustainable consumption, reduce food waste and avoid single-use materials which will be seen in the Human Experience (During) when students praise God through the Earth element. This is where students will witness to plant the potted flower in the soil and invites everyone to scoop soil and put it in the plant. The video showing the reality of Earth will be shown. On the third point students commit to sustainable ways of living which the fourth to sixth points lead to it such as consciously conserving energy, promoting eco-friendly and the likes. The

hopes that are elaborated in Human Experience (After) will come to its fruition when the students will make the commitment statement in making concrete steps in how they will show their social responsibility as stewards of God's creation.

ENVIRONMENTAL INTEGRATION

This integration “roots the catechesis in its total socio-religious, socio-cultural and environmental context”¹⁰ refer to the immediate setting. This includes where the students are coming from such as age group, familiar orientation, language, etc. In chapter 1: The Ground Plan situated the context of the Targeted Audience: The Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig. It was also mentioned in that same chapter the problem that dealt with the socio-cultural and environmental context of the students: stewards of God's creation and formation of conscience towards environmental stewardship. These contexts are reflected and further clarified as general context of each Ground Plan and is also seen in the subject which is found in Human Experience (Before). Across the Ground Plans, Environmental Integration is found in understanding the problem and how this will be addressed by the Christian Message and Objectives.

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, the problem states that Grade 7 students have not believe that they are innately good in result they do not see their connection with other creations that lead to abuse, negligence and harmful actions towards other creations. This problem focuses too much on the anthropological aspect seeing human beings as the center of God's creation and the only relevant other creations are those of human usage. The Christian Message states that “God is creating and sustaining each of us in

¹⁰ Ibid., para. 361.

existence. (CFC 339)” and Objectives proceeds, “explain that God is creating and sustaining each of us in existence. The teacher uses a table where the students will type the purpose of the mentioned object, then, the teacher will use Genesis 1:1-26: Creation Story to discuss that Genesis narrative reveals that each creation, God has purpose which gives meaning to its existence. Thus, Doctrine Christian message and Objectives addresses this situation.

In the Morals Ground Plan, the problem states that Grade 7 students think that conscience is always right, not considering that it depends on how it was formed. This problem lies on the misconceptions of students that Conscience is automatic. The Moral Christian Message and Objectives address this situation. The Morals Christian Message states that “We are morally obliged to form and educate our consciences to be truly informed, mature, and truly Christian.” and the Morals Objectives proceeds, “practice formative ways in forming the mind and heart to attain Christian conscience as they face choices everyday as they develop the sense of responsibility in obeying God’s law”. The students will be asked to list down their practices in forming their hearts and minds. The teacher will show the list of Christian ways in forming the two formative factors -heart and mind factors. The students will compare their personal practices to the Christian ways of forming the heart and mind. The teacher will also discuss that formation of one’s conscience depends on our countless interactions with parents, guardians, relatives, friends, and other members of the community. The way this is achieved is detailed in the objective, “practice formative ways” through article analysis “Greta Thunberg: The World's Youthful Climate Conscience” as the students put herself in the shoes of Greta and discern on how to promote ecological justice both for the environment and marginalized communities, to come up with sound decision considering factors and effects of their decisions.

In the WORSHIP Ground Plan, the problem states that Grade 7 students have a difficulty in taking “accountability in taking care of God’s creation as one of the social responsibilities. The teacher uses the 4 elements to intensify in valuing the commitment to caring the common home to exemplify one’s purpose, value and meaning in life.” The Worship Christian Message and Objectives addresses this situation. The Worship Christian Message states that “the value and purpose of creation is ultimately for the adoration of the Creator” and the Objectives proceeds, “profess the truth that we are creatures who owe our Creator adoration” to put emphasis on the accountability by being stewards of God’s creation. The problem will hopefully be addressed through student’s personal in-depth participation of the para-liturgy.

INCULTURATION

The second catechetical principle of FIRE methodology is inculturation. “On one hand, the Christian message must be expressed through images, symbols and rites that are indigenous to Filipino culture. On the other hand, authentic Filipino cultural values, attitudes, and practices must themselves be viewed in light of Christ and in terms of their basic dimensions.”¹¹

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, the teacher asked in Filipino language the question “Para kanino ka bumabangon?” to penetrate to the heart. It also follows with a question: “what hinders you to see your purpose?” to direct answers about their family. “The anak-magulang relationship is of primary importance to us Filipinos. *Ama, ina,* and *anak* are culturally and emotionally significant to us Filipinos who cherish our filial attachment not only to our immediate family, but also to our extended family (ninongs,

¹¹ Ibid., para. 369.

ninangs, etc.).”¹² In addition, in the mention of rest, the teacher will show different ways of Filipino games such as patintero, *tumbang preso* and *luksong baka*, and meal-oriented as one of the ways to value recreation. It can also be added to the family-meal as their way of bonding. Lastly, the activity on a dialogue with an object created by God shows our value of *kundiman* or putting a sentimental value to objects.

In the Morals Ground Plan, the Introduction points towards the happy and sad decisions they made, the factors they consider, the effects and if they can bring back time, would they make the same decision. In their personal answers most would come out of the Filipino cultural values, attitudes, and practices. This will be followed with an activity where students will be asked to list their personal practices in forming their hearts and minds. Possible answers such as family-oriented, meal-oriented, kundiman-oriented, spirit-oriented and religious practices will be highlighted. The teacher will then process that one of the factors in the formation of one’s conscience depends on our countless interactions with parents, guardians, relatives, friends and other members of the community to highlight the value on *pakikisama*.

In the WORSHIP Ground Plan, the students used symbols in making elements real such as—a candle for the element of fire, distilled and dirty water for water, an electric fan for the element of air, potted plants and soil for the element of earth. In the first half of the entire para-liturgy, the student will have a form of procession to go to each station which adapts to our Filipino practices for processions.

¹² Catholic Bishops’ Conference of the Philippines, *Catechism for Filipino Catholics*, para. 34.

COMMUNITY-FORMATION

The third catechetical principle of FIRE methodology is Community-Forming catechesis. “The life of faith is mediated, especially for the Filipino, in interpersonal dialogical encounters among those bound together by their belief in, witness to, and worship of, Jesus Christ our Lord.”¹³ Dyad or small group activity and sharing are best examples to bring out the “personal sense of intimacy, sharing and togetherness.”¹⁴

In the Doctrine Ground Plan, sharing of answers is an indicator that this principle of community-formation is shown in a way that when their classmates are called, they show respect by listening attentively. Their readiness as well to share their answer shows that they are willing to open and take part in the community in valuing “intimacy, sharing and togetherness”.

In the Morals Ground Plan the dyad activity is seen in the activity to recall decisions they made in the past and share their answer with their partner. The next activity is by group where students read and analyze the news article and share their answers to their group guided by the following questions: (1) If you are Greta, would you do the same? Why? Why not? (2) What are the factors that you consider in answering the 1st column? (3) What will be the possible effect/s of such decision? Then, they will brainstorm on how to answer the question: How would a person who has Christian conscience object to the climate crisis that greatly affected our poor brothers and sisters?

In the Worship Ground Plan, this principle is shown in a small group activity where students group by four which corresponds to the four elements namely fire,

¹³ *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines*, para. 384.

¹⁴ Catholic Bishops’ Conference of the Philippines, *Catechism for Filipino Catholics*, para. 387.

water, air and earth. Prior to the para-liturgy, the students were given time to work with their group on the different tasks such as a) research the situation of the 4 elements: Air, Water, Fire and Earth; b) provide evidence thru a 1-2 minute video or article showing the reality of the elements assigned to the group; c) promote hope in addressing the problem of the element through scriptural passages or scriptures; d) compose 4 ways as means to eliminate the problem of the element through prayer. Toward the end, the student is invited to form one big circle as they pray the “Prayers of the Faithful” in solidarity with the common goal of caring for the common home as their step in partaking in the solution.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SYNTHESIS

The project, which primarily aims to intensify the teaching of stewardship to Grade 7 students of St. Paul College Pasig in the subject CLVE. There is a need to acknowledge their responsibility as the crown of God's creation to seek oneness and solidarity with other creations. "A loving awareness that we are not disconnected from the rest of creatures, but joined in a splendid universal communion."¹ This aims to correct how students perceive themselves being created as "crown" of God's creation and to seek balance that human and non-human creations played an important role in the ecosystem. "These include the awareness of that each creature reflects something of God and has a message to convey to us, and the security that Christ has taken unto himself this material world and now, risen, is intimately present to each being, surrounding it with his affection and penetrating it with this light. Then too, there is the recognition that God created the world, writing into it an order and a dynamism that human beings have no right to ignore."²

The Teaching Statement is rooted in the deep reflection of how to teach students grow in faith which helps in the creation of the three Ground Plans to address the problem of this project: "How do we teach Grade 7 students of CLVE subject that stewardship is part of their moral responsibility?" It is in this light that "Religious

¹ Pope Francis, *Laudato Si*, para. 220.

² *Ibid.*, para. 221.

Education, in particular, should enable people to reflect critically on their own lives in the world, lend ready and well-informed access to the faith and then to make judgements and decisions about its truths and spiritual wisdom for their lives.”³ It is in the subject CLVE that Grade 7 students were taught to embrace the beautiful truth that we are created beautiful and good by God which leads to a deeper purpose of existence. This purpose will be achieved through the Formation of Conscience—“love the good and avoid evil” since conscience is not automatic, it needs to be formed gradually to take shape in our countless interactions... (CFC 704). “Good” here has the connection of being created “good” by God, therefore it is innate to take good care of other non-human creations to glorify God as well.

That is why there were three Ground Plans created for Grade 7 students: doctrine, morals and worship. The DOCTRINE Ground Plan entitled “God Creates and Sustains Everything that Exists” is a class encounter for 1 session that runs for 50 minutes. The MORALS Ground Plan entitled “Formation of Christian Conscience” is a class encounter for 1 session that runs for 50 minutes. The WORSHIP Ground Plan entitled “Care for the Common Home” is a paraliturgy for 50 minutes.

The Ground Plans following the FIRE (Formation Institute for Religion Education) are guided by three catechetical principles: integration, inculturation and community forming. “Integration, as the first principle of catechetical methodology, refers to the holistic, unified character of all authentic catechesis.”⁴ This is with one basic goal: to bring the good News into the totality of the person’s being involving the head, heart and hands. Integration in its forms and applications are Life Dimension,

³Groome, Thomas, *Will There Be Faith*, 97–98.

⁴ *New National Catechetical Directory for the Philippines*, para. 356.

Structural Integration, Dimension Integration, Source Integration, Subject Integration, and Environmental Integration.

Life integration is “to effectively bring the total inspiring message of Christ into the minds, wills and hearts of today’s Filipino.”⁵ This is seen in the Human Experiences: Before, During and After. The Human Experience During is an attempt to deliver the Christian Message in a step-by-step process. Structural Integration is the integration of Word, Witness and Worship to have a sound and effective catechetical method which can also be seen in the programs, class, or curriculum. This can be manifested in the parts of Christian Message and Objectives. Dimension integration “refers to the process of integrating multiple dimensions within each other of the three components of faith— Doctrine, Morals and Worship.”⁶ This helps to identify the order of priority, make solid connection and holistic integration. Source Integration seen in Sources and Means: Sacred Scripture, Church Teachings, Resources and how it manifested in the Human Experience During. Scripture, Tradition and Human Experience as primary sources of catechesis must be used creatively and adapted to the concrete catechesis being carried on. This is Subject integration gives a clear picture of the believer. This is seen in Human Experience: Before and After. Human Experience (Before) shows the multifaceted situation and context of the students that serves as the anchor on how to make the Christian message be known in the process of Human Experience (During) while Human Experience (After) elaborates the becoming or the hope that has been transpired. This project shows its strength as it covers the pre and pandemic status of the students which is vital in the creation of the Ground Plan. Lastly, Environmental

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid., para. 358.

integration includes where the students are coming from such as age group, familiar orientation, language, etc.

The second catechetical principle of FIRE methodology is inculturation. “On one hand, the Christian message must be expressed through images, symbols and rites that are indigenous to Filipino culture. On the other hand, authentic Filipino cultural values, attitudes, and practices must themselves be viewed in light of Christ and in terms of their basic dimensions.”⁷ This is evidently seen in all Ground Plans in the Human Experience (During).

The third catechetical principle of FIRE methodology is Community-Forming catechesis. “The life of faith is mediated, especially for the Filipino, in interpersonal dialogical encounters among those bound together by their belief in, witness to, and worship of, Jesus Christ our Lord.”⁸ Dyad or small group activity and sharing are best examples to bring out the “personal sense of intimacy, sharing and togetherness.”⁹ This is very evident in all Ground Plans through dyad, small and big groups activities.

This project is the culminating requirement in the RelEd 298: *Capstone Project* class, with the adviser Mr. Justin Joseph Badion. The course allows me to immerse in the depths of my vocation on how to teach students to mature in faith in my articulation of my teaching statement and in the creation of the Ground Plans which are analyze using the FIRE Methods by the narrative of its application of the catechetical principles. This paper is also an attempt to heed the urgency of the call for ecological conversion

⁷ Ibid., para. 369.

⁸ Ibid., para. 384.

⁹ Ibid., para. 387.

with the help of the encyclical letter of the Holy Father Francis on care for our common home—*Laudato Si*.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the writer's perspective, the following recommendations are:

1. The Ground Plans included herein were made in the different school years focusing on Grade 7 students. With this project, I recommend a developmental Ground Plan to be given to the same students as the progress to the next level. This will check their maturity and development as they take their roles of being the steward of God's creation with their formed conscience, evident in their worship of God for the gift of creations. On one hand, further and serious study on Ecological conversion can help support this project that can be given during their Senior High School.
2. It is recommended for future researchers conducting similar project to focus on the ecological conversion for human and non-human flourishing focusing on either Human Dignity or Human Freedom Morals Ground Plan to understand the effects of human acts towards our Common Home.
3. Lastly, effects of environmental change are extensively experienced by the poor. Pope Francis highlighted that the poor face the "worse impact" because they do not have the resources to adapt to climate change. It is recommended to have an intensive study of the effects of environmental change to the Poor.

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